

Comparative performance analysis of microchannel flat tube heat exchangers in thermochemical energy storage systems for water heating

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ABSTRACT

Open thermochemical energy storage (TCES) systems are usually for air heating and need a design evaluation for their connection with domestic central hot water systems. Our prior research introduced a TCES water heating system that incorporates an internal embedded bare microchannel flat tube heat exchanger (i.e., IBHEX-TCES system). Although simulations confirmed its feasibility, operational and maintenance challenges were noted, particularly in large-scale, multilayer TCES systems. To address these challenges, this study numerically investigated a novel configuration of the TCES water heating system that integrates a detached finned microchannel flat tube heat exchanger (i.e., DFHEX-TCES system), enhancing simplicity in practice. The performance comparison under identical conditions shows that in most scenarios, water temperature rises achieved by the IBHEX-TCES system are slightly higher by up to 0.7 °C, while the DFHEX-TCES system consistently maintains a 10 to 15 percentage point lead in the system's discharging thermal efficiency. These findings also apply to multilayer TCES systems, demonstrating the feasibility and benefits of using DFHEX instead of IBHEX in multilayer TCES systems for large-scale applications. The use of DFHEX not only enhances the system discharging performance but also significantly eases operational and maintenance challenges.

1. Introduction

The global energy landscape is currently experiencing notable transformations driven by the post-pandemic economic recovery and increasing regional tensions [1]. Escalating fossil fuel prices has resulted in an unprecedented energy crisis, highlighting the urgent need to transition towards renewable energy sources, with solar energy being particularly promising. Solar energy offers tremendous potential to alleviate the current energy scarcity [2]. However, the variable output of solar energy creates difficulties in achieving a balance between supply and demand. To ensure sustainability and resilience in energy supply, these challenges must be surmounted [3]. Thermal energy storage (TES) technology is acknowledged as an effective approach to managing the mismatch between supply and demand in solar energy systems. This technology stores excess thermal energy produced by solar systems and releases it when heat is needed by users [4]. TES technologies are typically delineated into three fundamental categories: sensible thermal energy storage (STES) [5], latent thermal energy storage (LTES) [6], and thermochemical energy storage (TCES) [7]. The energy storage densities

(ESDs) of STES and LTES technologies are approximately 0.25 GJ m⁻³ and 0.5 GJ m⁻³, respectively [8]. By way of contrast, TCES technology demonstrates a superior energy storage density (i.e., >1 GJ m⁻³) [9], enhancing its appeal for widespread integration in solar energy systems [2]. Furthermore, TCES systems convert thermal energy into chemical potential during the charging process, rendering heat losses negligible during the storage period [10].

Salt hydrates as widely used thermochemical materials (TCMs) show significant promise because of their low charging temperatures [11], cost-effectiveness [12], and non-toxicity properties [13]. In the salt hydrate-based TCES system, salt hydrates (Salt·xH₂O) absorb thermal energy from a low-grade heat source, this leads to the breaking of molecular bonds within salt hydrates, resulting in the dissociation into salts and water molecules, and heat is converted into chemical potential for storage in this process (i.e., the charging process). Conversely, when salts are exposed to water vapor or moist air, they recombine with water molecules, forming new chemical bonds and releasing heat (i.e., the discharging process) [14]. The operational principles of salt hydrates are outlined below:

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Despite their potential, salt hydrates often demonstrate inadequate thermal and mass transfer properties. These shortcomings can precipitate problems such as agglomeration and expansion, which in turn can compromise both the thermal efficiency and cycle stability of TCES systems [15]. One feasible solution to overcome these challenges is to incorporate a TCES composite material, which combines salt hydrates with a porous matrix (e.g., silica gel [16], expanded graphite [17], expanded vermiculite [9] and zeolites [18]). The porous structure of porous matrices effectively enhances mass transfer performance and prevents uneven reaction and agglomeration, thereby improving the thermal efficiency and cyclic stability of TCES systems [19].

At present, two main categories of TCES reactors exist open systems and closed systems [20]. The typical open TCES system consists solely of a reactor, whose interior contains only reaction beds that carry TCMs. Air, acting as the working gas in the open system, serves both as the mass transfer fluid and the heat transfer medium. This simple configuration enables the widespread application of open TCES systems [21]. Recent research has focused on enhancing the performance of reactors open systems by refining the reactor structural design, for instance, the integration of air diffusers [22], multi-module configurations [23], and fluidized bed design [24]. Nevertheless, issues may arise in open TCES system where the heat generated during the discharging process is not promptly dissipated, resulting in elevated reactor temperatures that can suppress the hydration reaction rate [8]. Additionally, since all the heat released in open systems dissipates into the air, they currently cannot be readily integrated into the predominantly water-based central heating systems used in most regional households. This limitation necessitates the incorporation of an additional substantial network of household air ducts, thereby increasing equipment investment.

Alternatively, the typical closed TCES system includes a highly sealed vacuumed reactor, as well as an evaporator, a condenser, and a water tank. The reactor in this closed system features more than just a reaction bed; it also incorporates integrated heat exchangers. These heat exchangers are crucial for transferring heat generated during the discharge process from the reaction bed to the heat transfer medium, and subsequently conveying this heat outside the system. Various types and structures of heat exchangers (e.g., trapezoidal aluminium tube-and-fin heat exchanger [25], fin plate heat exchanger [26], honeycomb heat exchanger [27] and bundle-type heat exchanger [28]) have been developed and investigated for closed systems. The primary advantage of closed TCES systems is their ability to facilitate direct integration into domestic central heating systems. This integration eliminates the need for extensive retrofitting investments. However, closed TCES systems require numerous additional components, and the reactor must operate under sealed vacuum conditions, significantly increasing the overall system cost. Moreover, since heat exchangers are typically embedded within the reaction bed, this complicates operations during the addition or replacement of TCMs and exposes the heat exchangers to the risk of corrosion.

This study introduces a novel open TCES water heating solution, which incorporates a detached finned microchannel tube air-to-water heat exchanger within an open TCES system. This configuration, named DFHEX-TCES, features a simple composition and operates under non-sealed conditions, allowing for direct integration into existing domestic central heating systems. As a result, this approach minimizes room modification costs while also reducing the energy consumption and construction costs typically associated with maintaining a vacuum environment. Moreover, the DFHEX-TCES utilizes a detached heat exchanger, which eliminates the direct contact between the heat exchanger and TCMs, a typical feature of traditional closed TCES systems. Similar issues are also found in previously proposed open TCES water heating systems featuring an integrated bare microchannel tube air-to-water heat exchanger (IBHEX-TCES) [29]. By reducing the risk of

corrosion from direct exposure to TCMs, this innovative solution enhances the operability of filling and replacing TCMs. To validate the feasibility of this system, a COMSOL model of the DFHEX-TCES system was developed and used for comparative assessment against the previously proposed IBHEX-TCES water heating system. Based on these numerical models, extensive analysis was conducted to evaluate how different operational and structural parameters affect the performance of the DFHEX-TCES and IBHEX-TCES systems. Additionally, the study explored the use of DFHEX in a multilayer TCES system, assessing its feasibility as a suitable alternative to IBHEX in large-scale multilayer TCES reactors. These findings provide new insights into the practicality and maintenance of TCES water heating systems, particularly for large-scale multilayer TCES systems.

2. System description

Fig. 1 illustrates the DFHEX-TCES water heating system configuration and workflow during the discharging/charging process. This system primarily consists of a TCES reactor integrated with a detached finned microchannel heat exchanger (DFHEX), a heat recovery unit (HRU), a low-temperature heat source (e.g., solar collector), an air fan, and a humidifier. In the discharging process, the cold air into the HRU and is preheated by the exhaust discharged from the reactor. The preheated air then directly enters the humidifier, where it is humidified. Subsequently, this humidified air enters the TCES reactor and passes through the TCES reaction bed. Here, the salt in the TCES composite materials hydrates by absorbing moisture from the air and releases heat, thereby heating the air. After passing through the reaction bed, the heated and dried air is directed to the DFHEX at the reactor's end. In the DFHEX, heat from the air is partially transferred to the thermal exchange medium (i.e., water), which is then directed to the domestic central heating system. The remaining heat is carried out of the reactor with the air; a portion of this residual heat is recovered by the HRU, while the remainder is expelled into the surrounding environment. During the charging process, preheated air enters the solar collector where it is further heated to a higher temperature. The high temperature air then flows into the reactor and passes through the reaction bed, causing the salt hydrates in the composite to dehydrate under the high-temperature environment and absorb heat from the air. During the charging process, the water inside the DFHEX remains stagnant and does not significantly affect the overall system. The cooled air exits the reactor after passing through the DFHEX and then the exhaust enters the HRU, where residual heat is utilized to preheat the incoming cold air.

In this TCES water heating system, the reactor consists of a reaction bed and a DFHEX, their structure shown in Fig. 2(a). The reaction bed is constructed from metal mesh and measures 280 mm × 280 mm × 50 mm (Length × Width × Height). This reaction bed is filled with thermochemical materials (TCMs). The DFHEX has the same frontal area as the reaction bed and includes ten water channels extending across the bed. Each water channel features a 2 mm width alongside a 50 mm height, with a spacing of 26 mm between the adjacent water channels. In addition, one hundred fins are oriented perpendicular to water channels and evenly distributed between them. These fins are welded at both ends to the adjacent side surfaces of the water channels. Notably, these fins have the same height as the water channels and are spaced at intervals of 2.7 mm.

To evaluate the newly introduced DFHEX-TCES system performance, the previously proposed IBHEX-TCES system, which incorporates an internal bare microchannel flat tube heat exchanger (IBHEX), was also subjected to simulation testing as a comparative case. These two systems exhibit variations in the placement and design of their heat exchangers (i.e., with or without fins), while all other system components are identical. In the IBHEX-TCES system, the embedded configuration of the IBHEX within the reaction bed allows for considering these two components as a single combined unit (see Fig. 2(b)).

In both TCES water heating systems, the reaction beds are filled with

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the TCES water heating system in (a) discharging process; (b) charging process.

Fig. 2. 3D diagrams of (a) the TCES reaction bed and DFHEX in DFHEX-TCES reactor; (b) the TCES reaction bed with embedded IBHEX unit in the IBHEX-TCES reactor [29].

vermiculite-CaCl₂ synthesized using the single-step impregnation method from previous research [17]. According to prior studies, the gravimetric energy storage density of vermiculite-CaCl₂ is approximately 2232 kJ kg⁻¹. When the reaction bed is fully filled with vermiculite-CaCl₂, the volumetric energy storage density of the single-layer DFHEX-TCES reactor is about 70 kWh·m⁻³, while that of the single-layer IBHEX-TCES reactor is close to 130 kWh·m⁻³. The primary reason for the lower volumetric energy density in the single-layer DFHEX-TCES reactor is that its internal detached heat exchanger occupies about half of the space. In the design of multi-layer structures, the volumetric energy storage densities of both types of TCES water heating reactors approach 100 kWh·m⁻³.

3. Mathematical model

The TCES models utilized here are those established and reported in our prior numerical study [30]. Table 1 provides a summary of the control equations relevant to reaction kinetics, mass balance, mass transfer, and energy balance. Additionally, to develop a mathematical model that describes the mass and energy transfer within the TCES water heating system, the following assumptions are made.

- (1) TCMs and the airflow are assumed to be in local thermal equilibrium within the reactor [31,32].
- (2) Radiative heat transfer is not considered in the TCES water heating system [33,34].
- (3) The airflow is considered an ideal gas and follows Darcy's law [35].
- (4) TCMs are evenly distributed in perforated plate trays, and the effect of perforated plates on the dehydration/hydration of TCMS was considered negligible [36].

3.1. Energy balance of air-to-water heat exchanger

In the air to water microchannel heat exchanger, the thermal energy transfer process from air to water involves air, aluminum microchannel plates, and water. The Heat Transfer module in COMSOL Multiphysics is used to simulate the solid-fluid coupled heat exchange process in the air to water microchannel heat exchanger. The Heat Transfer module in COMSOL can handle energy transfer in solid and fluid media, including conduction and convection. This module supports automatic handling of heat flux and temperature matching at the solid-fluid interface, ensuring the continuity and conservation of energy. This energy transfer process

can be described by the following energy conservation equation:

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \lambda \nabla^2 T - C \rho \vec{u} \nabla T \quad (9)$$

3.2. Initial and boundaries conditions

In the initial phase of the study, it is assumed that temperature, pressure, degree of conversion, and vapor concentration are uniformly distributed throughout the TCES reactor. The reactor is set to an initial temperature of 20 °C and an initial pressure of 101.325 kPa. Considering the emphasis of this investigation on the discharging process, the initial conversion degree of the salt hydrates is established at 1. Airflow parameters, including temperature, relative humidity, and velocity, are held constant at the reactor's inlet. Non-slip boundary conditions are applied along the reactor walls. As the TCES system operates openly, the operational pressure of the reactor is maintained equal to the standard atmospheric pressure (i.e., p_{ref}). It is assumed that the temperature differential at the reactor's outlet is negligible. Furthermore, the mass flux at the outlet boundary is predominantly governed by convection, with diffusive mass flux considered insignificant at this stage.

Given that the TCES reactor is typically positioned indoors, its surface air velocity is nearly negligible. Consequently, natural convection heat transfer predominates as the mode of thermal exchange with the environment. Therefore, the energy conservation equation at the reactor's boundary is described as:

$$-\mathbf{n}(\lambda_{ins} \nabla T) = h_{ins}(T_{amb} - T) \quad (10)$$

where λ_{ins} is the thermal conductivity of the insulating material, $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$; h_{ins} is the natural convective heat transfer coefficient between the reactor and ambient air, $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$; and T_{amb} is the ambient air temperature, K.

3.3. Performance metrics

This study determines the discharging thermal efficiency of the TCES water heating system during discharging by calculating the ratio of heat captured by the waterflow to the thermal energy liberated from the hydration of TCMS. The equation is as follows:

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{Q_{ab}}{Q_{re}} \quad (11)$$

where Q_{ab} and Q_{re} are the amount of thermal energy captured by waterflow and thermal energy liberated from the hydration of TCMS,

Table 1
Control equations relevant to reaction kinetics, mass balance, mass transfer, and energy balance in TCES reactor [30,32,33].

Theory	Equation
Reaction kinetics	
Clausius-Clapeyron relationship	
Mass balance	$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = R_{kin} \alpha \left(1 - \frac{p_v}{p_{eq}}\right) = A_{freq} \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \alpha \left(1 - \frac{p_v}{p_{eq}}\right)$ (2)
Momentum balance	$\ln\left(\frac{p_{eq}}{p_{ref}}\right) = -\frac{\Delta H_r}{RT_{ref}} + \frac{\Delta S_r}{R}$ (3)
Energy balance	$\varepsilon \frac{\partial \rho_v}{\partial t} = S_w - \nabla(\rho_v \vec{u}) + D_g \Delta \rho_v$ (4)
	$S_w = z c_{s,i} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} M_v$ (5)
	$\varepsilon \frac{\partial \rho_a}{\partial t} = S_w - \nabla(\rho_a \vec{u})$ (6)
	$\frac{\rho_a}{\varepsilon} \frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} + \frac{\rho_a \vec{u} \nabla \vec{u}}{\varepsilon^2} = \nabla \left[-\bar{p}_a \mathbf{1} + \frac{\mu}{\varepsilon} \left(\nabla \vec{u} + (\nabla \vec{u})^T - \frac{2\mu}{3\varepsilon} (\nabla \cdot \vec{u}) \mathbf{I} \right) \right] + S_w \frac{\vec{u}}{\varepsilon^2} - \frac{\mu}{\varepsilon} \vec{u}$ (7)
	$(1 - \varepsilon) \rho_s C_s \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla(\lambda_{eff} \nabla T) - C_a \rho_a \vec{u} \nabla T - z c_{s,i} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \Delta H_r$ (8)

respectively, kJ.

The amount of thermal energy captured by waterflow is described as:

$$Q_{ab} = \int C_w \dot{m}_w (T_{w,out} - T_{w,in}) dt \quad (12)$$

where \dot{m}_w is the waterflow mass flow rate, $\text{kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$; $T_{w,out}$ and $T_{w,in}$ are the inlet and outlet waterflow temperatures of the water channel, respectively, K.

The amount of thermal energy liberated from the hydration of TCMS is described as:

$$Q_{re} = - \int \int z_{c,s,i} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \Delta H_r dt dV \quad (13)$$

Table 2 lists the key parameters of the TCES composite materials (i. e., vermiculite- CaCl_2), TCES reaction bed, and DFHEX used in this numerical study, along with their respective values.

4. Software setup and model validation

This numerical study utilizes the transient solver in COMSOL Multiphysics 6.1 to simulate the performance of the TCES water heating systems. The flowchart illustrating the numerical simulation is presented in Fig. 3. The governing equations for thermochemical reactions, mass transfer, momentum transfer, and heat transfer within the reaction bed are described by Equations (2) and (6)–(8), respectively. Additionally, the energy balance in the water channels of the heat exchanger is detailed in Section 3.1. The simulation time step is set at 10 s, utilizing the backward differentiation formula (BDF) method for calculating the time steps. The Generalized Minimal Residual Method (GMRES) is employed as the iterative solver, with a residual value set at 10^{-6} to

Table 2

Thermophysical properties of TCES composite materials and parameters of the TCES water heating system.

Parameters	Description	Value
M_v	Molecular mass of vapor ($\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)	18.02
M_s	Molecular mass of salt hydrate ($\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)	219.08
$c_{s,i}$	Molar concentration ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	1100
k	Permeability of TCES composite materials (m^2)	$8.24 \bullet 10^{-6}$
C_s	Specific heat of the TCES composite materials ($\text{J} \bullet \text{kg}^{-1} \bullet \text{K}^{-1}$)	626
λ_s	Thermal conductivity of TCES composite materials ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)	0.0669
ϵ	Porosity	0.64
E_a	Activation energy ($\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)	44700 [37]
ΔH_r	Reaction enthalpy ($\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)	60216 [17]
ΔS_r	Reaction entropy ($\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	153 [38]
D_g	Gas diffusion coefficient ($\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)	$2.3\cdot 10^{-8}$
C_a	Specific heat of the airflow ($\text{J} \bullet \text{g}^{-1} \bullet \text{K}^{-1}$)	1.006
R	Universal gas constant ($\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)	8.314
p_{ref}	Reference pressure (Pa)	101325
C_{Al}	Specific heat of the aluminium water channels ($\text{J} \bullet \text{g}^{-1} \bullet \text{K}^{-1}$)	0.897
ρ_{Al}	Density of the aluminium water channels ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	2700
λ_{Al}	Thermal conductivity of the aluminium water channels ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)	209
C_w	Specific heat of the water ($\text{J} \bullet \text{g}^{-1} \bullet \text{K}^{-1}$)	4.184
ρ_w	Density of the water ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	1000
$T_{in,a}$	Airflow temperature at system inlet ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	20
$T_{in,w}$	Waterflow temperature at HEX inlet ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	27
λ_{ins}	Thermal conductivity of the insulating material ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)	0.035
L	Length of the reaction bed (m)	0.280
W	Width of the reaction bed (m)	0.280
H	Height of the reaction bed (m)	0.05
l	Length of the DFHEX waterflow channel (m)	0.28
w	Width of the DFHEX waterflow channel (m)	0.002
h	Height of the DFHEX waterflow channel (m)	0.05

ensure numerical stability and convergence of the simulation results. Following a grid independence analysis, a fine mesh is identified as the optimal computational grid for this study.

To validate the mathematical model described previously, this study developed a TCES system (see Fig. 4) and conducted individual tests on both the reactor and the microchannel flat tube HEX. This TCES system mainly consists of a humidifier, a heater, a reactor, and data collection instruments. The reaction bed and microchannel flat tube HEX are individually placed inside the reactor for experimental testing. The reaction bed is made of 1 mm metal mesh measuring $28 \text{ cm} \times 28 \text{ cm} \times 5 \text{ cm}$ (Length \times Width \times Height) and is filled with TCES composite materials (i.e., vermiculite- CaCl_2). The microchannel flat tube HEX comprises three aluminium microchannel flat tubes, each with a width of 2 mm. Identical models of the reactor and microchannel flat tube HEX were developed in COMSOL using the proposed mathematical model in section 3. The comparison of simulation results and experimental data utilized the root mean square deviation (RMSD) as the quantification metric, which is expressed by the equation below [39]:

$$RMSD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum [(x_{sim,i} - x_{exp,i}) / x_{exp,i}]^2}{n}} \quad (14)$$

Fig. 5 presents the validation experimental flowchart and Fig. 6 illustrates the schematic diagram of the experimental setup for the reactor and microchannel flat tube heat exchanger. During the validation experiment for the reactor, the electric heater was turned off and the humidifier was activated, setting the air inlet conditions to 20°C and 55 % relative humidity. The humid air entered the reactor, where it was absorbed by the CaCl_2 in the reaction bed, triggering the hydration reaction and releasing heat, subsequently, the heated air exited the reactor. Fig. 7(a) shows the experimental data for the temperature changes at the reactor outlet, which exhibited a rapid initial increase, reaching peak temperatures of 39.89°C at approximately 13th minutes. Following this peak, the temperature gradually declined until the end of the experiment. In the validation of the microchannel flat tube heat exchanger, the electric heater was used to heat the air, while a constant temperature water bath supplied a steady flow of water. The inlet temperatures for the air and water were set at 50°C and 20°C , respectively. The experimental data for the water temperature at the heat exchanger outlet initially rose rapidly and then gradually stabilized around 27°C after 10 min, as shown in Fig. 7(b).

In the validation experiment, only the air outlet temperature of the reactor and water outlet temperature of the heat exchanger were measured. The uncertainty percentages for these measurements were directly related to the sensor measurement errors. The air outlet temperature was measured using a Sensirion SHT45 Digital Humidity and Temperature Sensor, while the water outlet temperature was measured with an Electrotherm 282 RS thermocouple. After calibration, the errors for these sensors were determined to be $\pm 0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\pm 0.05^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. Based on these errors, the maximum calculated uncertainty percentages for the air outlet temperature and the water outlet temperature were found to be 0.25 % and 0.19 %, respectively.

Using the previously established mathematical model, reactor and heat exchanger models with the same structure and materials as those in the validation experiments were developed and simulated. The simulated results for both the reactor outlet air temperature and the heat exchanger outlet water temperature are also displayed in Fig. 7. Throughout the process, the average temperature difference between the experimental and simulated conditions for the reactor outlet air temperature was about 0.30°C , with an RMSD value of 1.98 %. The difference between the experimental data and simulation data for the heat exchanger outlet water temperature was minimal, with an RMSD value of 0.65 %. These comparison results validate that the mathematical model can accurately predict the performance of the proposed TCES system and the microchannel flat tube heat exchanger. In establishing the TCES reactor model, several key assumptions were made. A

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the numerical simulation process.

Fig. 4. Images of the multifunctional lab-sized TCES system along with its components.

significant assumption is that the TCMs within the reactor are in thermal equilibrium with the airflow. While this assumption simplifies the simulation of heat exchange between the TCMs and the airflow, it may introduce errors, particularly in scenarios characterized by slow heat transfer or complex conditions. Additionally, the hydration of CaCl_2 during the simulation was modeled as a continuous process, rather than as a staged hydration reaction, which occurs in practice. This simplification was primarily implemented to address the complexities associated with coupled multiphysics phenomena and to ensure numerical

modelling convergence.

5. Results and discussion

In accordance with the mathematical model previously developed, this study utilized COMSOL Multiphysics to conduct numerical analyses of three TCES water heating systems. The objective was to evaluate and compare their thermal performance under varying operational parameters. These three TCES water heating systems are listed as follows: the

Fig. 5. Flowchart of the validation experiment.

previously researched IBHEX-TCES system, which integrates an internal bare HEX and a heat recovery unit (HRU); the newly proposed DFHEX-TCES system in this study, featuring a finned detached HEX and an HRU; and the DBHEX-TCES system that incorporates an end-positioned bare HEX and an HRU. Table 3 lists a detailed description of the three system configurations.

5.1. Effect of heat exchanger location and fins scheme

This section evaluates and compares the thermal performance of these three TCES water heating systems throughout the entire discharging process under benchmark conditions. Lower outdoor air temperatures typical of winter can lead to reduced conversion rates and slower heat release in TCMs due to the diminished moisture-carrying capacity of low-temperature air, adversely affecting both system performance and efficiency. Therefore, using cold outdoor air directly in TCES systems during winter is typically impractical. To address this challenge, humidified warm indoor air is introduced into the TCES system in this study. The benchmark condition assumes that the treated airflow has a temperature of 20 °C, an absolute humidity of 10 g kg⁻¹, and an airflow mass flow rate of 0.0019 kg s⁻¹ (i.e., corresponding to a vertical air velocity of 0.02 m s⁻¹ through the reaction bed). The inlet

waterflow temperature and mass flow rate for the air-to-water HEX are set at 27 °C and 0.0016 kg s⁻¹, respectively.

The thermal performance of these TCES systems incorporating air-to-water HEX is analyzed and compared, and their outlet water temperature variations are presented in Fig. 8. These curves show a rapid initial rise, peaking around the 10th minute. The peak outlet water temperatures for the two systems with finless bare heat exchangers (i.e., IBHEX-TCES and DBHEX-TCES systems) are recorded at 35.15 °C and 33 °C, respectively. This difference is due to the IBHEX-TCES system's internal heat exchanger being directly exposed to the TCMs, allowing quicker heat absorption from the salt hydrates compared to the end-positioned exchanger. On the other hand, the DFHEX-TCES system, integrating a finned air-to-water HEX demonstrates a higher peak outlet waterflow temperature of 34.59 °C compared to the DBHEX-TCES system, showcasing a 1.59 °C increase due to the enhanced heat exchange surface area by the fins, facilitating more effective thermal exchange. Despite the lower peak temperatures compared to the IBHEX-TCES system, both DFHEX-TCES and DBHEX-TCES systems have extended durations (expressed as t_d), where the water temperature lifts remain above 5 °C (considered directly utilizable thermal energy). In particular, the DFHEX-TCES system extends this duration by 67 min reaching nearly six and a half hours, while the DBHEX-TCES system extends it by 38 min, totalling 6 h. Moreover, the overall duration of water heating capability is increased by 60 min for the DFHEX-TCES system and 105 min for the DBHEX-TCES system, respectively.

The heat absorbed by the waterflow and the discharging thermal efficiency (η_{th}) of these three TCES systems during the discharging process is presented in Table 4. The two TCES systems incorporating finless air-to-water heat exchangers (i.e., IBHEX-TCES and DBHEX-TCES) demonstrate similar heat absorption by the water flow during discharging, at 1272 kJ and 1252 kJ, respectively. However, the DFHEX-TCES system exhibits a notable increase in heat absorption, reaching 1430 kJ. This represents increases of 12.42 % and 14.22 % over the IBHEX-TCES and DBHEX-TCES systems, respectively. The enhancement in heat absorption is attributed to the fins enlarging the thermal exchange surface area, facilitating enhanced thermal transfer from airflow to waterflow in the HEX during the discharging process. Simultaneously, the DFHEX-TCES system achieves the highest efficiency at 92 %, while the other two TCES systems both reach efficiency levels around 80 %.

Fig. 6. Schematic illustration of the experimental rig for validation of TCES reactor and heat exchanger.

Fig. 7. Simulation and experimental results of (a) air temperature at TCES reactor outlet and (b) water temperature at air-to-water HEX outlet.

Table 3

The structure and installation location of HEX in three TCES systems.

Systems	HEX Configuration	HEX Position
IBHEX-TCES	Internal bare air-to-water HEX	Embedded in reaction bed
DFHEX-TCES	Detached finned air-to-water HEX	After the reaction bed (detached from the reaction bed)
DBHEX-TCES	Detached bare air-to-water HEX	After the reaction bed (detached from the reaction bed)

Fig. 8. Outlet water temperatures of IBHEX-TCES, DBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems.

Table 4

Heat absorbed by the waterflow and the overall thermal efficiencies of IBHEX-TCES, DBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems during the discharging process.

	IBHEX-TCES	DBHEX-TCES	DFHEX-TCES
Q_{reaction}	1559	1546	1554
$Q_{\text{w,ab}}$ (kJ)	1272	1252	1430
η_{th} (%)	82	81	92

5.2. Combined effect of inlet airflow and waterflow temperatures

Airflow and waterflow inlet temperatures are critical in determining the discharging efficiency of TCES water heating systems. This section assesses the impact of inlet temperatures of airflow and waterflow on the maximum temperature lift ($\Delta T_{\text{MAX,w}}$) and η_{th} of the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems. In addition, the discharging performance of both systems under identical inlet temperature conditions is compared. The inlet temperature of airflow varies between 15 °C and 25 °C, whereas the inlet temperature of waterflow is set between 25 °C and 30 °C. All other conditions are consistent with those outlined in Section 5.1.

Fig. 9 illustrates the impact of the inlet temperatures of airflow and waterflow on the $\Delta T_{\text{MAX,w}}$ and η_{th} of the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems. In both systems, the $\Delta T_{\text{MAX,w}}$ widens with the rising inlet airflow temperature. This occurs because an increase in airflow temperature leads to a decrease in the inlet temperature difference between the airflow and waterflow. Consequently, more heat generated by salt hydrates can be effectively transferred to the waterflow rather than elevating the airflow temperature to match that of the waterflow. For example, with the inlet water temperature set at 25 °C, raising the airflow temperature from 15 °C to 25 °C leads to an elevation of the $\Delta T_{\text{MAX,w}}$ in both systems. Specifically, the $\Delta T_{\text{MAX,w}}$ widens from 7.77 °C to 8.55 °C in the IBHEX-TCES system and from 7.45 °C to 8.05 °C in the DFHEX-TCES system.

However, when the inlet waterflow temperature rises, the $\Delta T_{\text{MAX,w}}$ in both systems declines, due to the diminishing temperature gradient between the water flow and the TCMS or the heated airflow. This smaller temperature differential curtails heat transfer efficiency between the heat source (i.e., TCMS or heated airflow) and the waterflow. As the inlet waterflow temperature increases from 25 °C to 30 °C and the airflow maintains an inlet temperature of 15 °C, the $\Delta T_{\text{MAX,w}}$ in the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems drops to 7.35 °C and 6.91 °C, respectively. Under the same conditions of airflow and waterflow inlet temperatures, the $\Delta T_{\text{MAX,w}}$ in the IBHEX-TCES system consistently remains slightly higher than in the DFHEX-TCES, but the difference does not exceed 0.7 °C.

The impact of inlet temperatures on the η_{th} of the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems is similar to their effect on $\Delta T_{\text{MAX,w}}$. As the inlet airflow temperature increases, more heat generated by the TCMS is transferred to the water flow, rather than being used to raise the airflow temperature to match that of the waterflow. Consequently, the η_{th} of both systems improves. Conversely, the η_{th} decreases when the inlet

Fig. 9. Effects of the inlet temperatures of airflow and waterflow on the maximum temperature lift and discharging thermal efficiency of the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems.

waterflow temperature increases. Within the investigated range, the η_{th} of the IBHEX-TCES system consistently remains below 85 %, while the DFHEX-TCES system mostly exceeds 90 %, and in some cases, even reaches up to 95 %. Under identical operating conditions, the η_{th} of the DFHEX-TCES system surpasses that of the IBHEX-TCES system, leading by as much as 10 percentage points. Despite the slightly higher $\Delta T_{MAX,w}$ in the IBHEX-TCES system, the DFHEX-TCES system maintains a clear lead in discharging thermal efficiency.

5.3. Combined effect of airflow and waterflow mass flow rates

This section investigates the combined effect of airflow and waterflow mass flow rates on thermal performance of the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems. The airflow mass flow rate is adjusted between 0.0015 and 0.0035 kg s^{-1} , while the waterflow mass flow rate spans 0.001–0.003 kg s^{-1} . As displayed in Fig. 10, both systems experience a rise in peak outlet waterflow temperatures as airflow mass flow rates increase, due to heightened convective heat transfer coefficients that boost the heat exchange between airflow and waterflow. For instance,

when the waterflow mass flow rate is 0.001 kg s^{-1} and the airflow mass flow rate rises from 0.0015 kg s^{-1} to 0.0035 kg s^{-1} , the peak outlet waterflow temperatures for the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems rise from 37.58 °C to 37.06 °C–44.29 °C and 43.75 °C, respectively. Conversely, the peak outlet waterflow temperatures decline as the waterflow mass flow rate rises, because although the convective heat transfer coefficient is higher, the water's residence time in the heat exchanger is shorter, leading to less heat being absorbed. For example, when the airflow mass flow rate is 0.0015 kg s^{-1} and the waterflow mass flow rate increases from 0.001 kg s^{-1} to 0.003 kg s^{-1} , the peak outlet waterflow temperatures for the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems reduce to 29.52 °C and 30.35 °C, respectively. In most simulation scenarios, the peak outlet waterflow temperature of the IBHEX-TCES system is slightly higher than that of the DFHEX-TCES system, but the difference is consistently less than 1 °C.

The mass flow rate has opposite effects on the discharging thermal efficiency and peak outlet waterflow temperatures of the two systems. With rising airflow mass flow rates, the η_{th} of both systems declines. This is due to the shorter air residence time in the HEX, which reduces heat

Fig. 10. Effects of the airflow and waterflow mass flow rates on the peak outlet waterflow temperature and discharging thermal efficiency of the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems.

Fig. 11. The impact of the absolute humidity of the reactor inlet airflow on (a) peak temperature of outlet waterflow and (b) duration of waterflow temperature lifts remain above 5 °C of DFHEX-TCES and IBHEX-TCES systems.

transfer to the water despite a higher convective heat transfer coefficient. In contrast, As the waterflow mass flow rate augments, the η_{th} of both systems improves due to the enhanced effectiveness of the HEX, allowing more heat to be transferred from the airflow to the waterflow. Within the simulation range, the η_{th} of the IBHEX-TCES system typically remains below 85 %, whereas the DFHEX-TCES system generally exceeds 85 %, and in some cases, even reaches above 95 %. Under the same operation conditions, The DFHEX-TCES system exhibits higher η_{th} compared to the IBHEX-TCES system, with a maximum lead of nearly 12 percentage points. Similar to the inlet temperature findings in Section 5.2, although the $\Delta T_{MAX,w}$ of the IBHEX-TCES system is slightly higher than that of the DFHEX-TCES system within the mass flow rate varying range, the difference is minor. However, in terms of η_{th} , the DFHEX-TCES system demonstrates better performance than the IBHEX-TCES system.

5.4. Effect of absolute humidity of reactor inlet airflow

The absolute humidity significantly influences the hydration process of TCMS within the reactor. This section explores the effect of the airflow absolute humidity on the discharging performance of the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES water heating systems integrated with air-to-water heat HEX of different structures and installation positions. Assuming the inlet airflow absolute humidity varies within the range of 7–12 g kg⁻¹, with all other parameters consistent with those stated in Section 5.1.

The effect of the inlet airflow absolute humidity on the outlet waterflow peak temperatures of these two TCES systems is illustrated in Fig. 11(a). As the inlet airflow absolute humidity rises, the outlet waterflow peak temperatures of both IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems increase. This is because the higher inlet airflow absolute humidity raises the water vapor's partial pressure inside the reactor, thereby enhancing the salt's conversion rate in the TCES composite materials (as per Eq. (3)). As a consequence, more heat is released and transferred to the waterflow (as described by Eq. (10)). At lower absolute humidities (i.e., absolute humidity = 7 g kg⁻¹), the peak waterflow temperature at the outlet of the DFHEX-TCES system is slightly higher than that of the IBHEX-TCES system, with temperatures of 32.84 °C and 32.55 °C, respectively. However, with an increase in inlet airflow absolute humidity, the peak water temperature in the IBHEX-TCES system rises more rapidly than in the DFHEX-TCES system. When the inlet airflow absolute humidity reaches 8 g kg⁻¹, these two systems exhibit the same peak waterflow temperature. With a continued rise in inlet airflow absolute humidity, the peak water temperature in the IBHEX-TCES system exceeds that in the DFHEX-TCES system, and this disparity continues to widen. At an inlet airflow absolute humidity of 10 g kg⁻¹, the peak waterflow temperatures of the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems are 37.03 °C and 35.74 °C, respectively, showing a difference of 1.29 °C.

Both systems demonstrate a similar trend in the duration (expressed as t_d) when waterflow temperature lifts remain above 5 °C with increasing inlet airflow absolute humidity, as illustrated in Fig. 11(b). The t_d of the DFHEX-TCES and IBHEX-TCES systems increases with the inlet airflow absolute humidity until it reaches a peak at 9 g kg⁻¹, at 398 min and 328 min, respectively. Increased inlet airflow absolute humidity elevates outlet waterflow temperatures, thereby prolonging the t_d values. Upon exceeding 9 g kg⁻¹ of absolute humidity, the t_d decreases in both systems due to accelerated reaction rates facilitating more rapid heat release. The t_d in the DFHEX-TCES system consistently remains longer than in the IBHEX-TCES system under the same inlet airflow absolute humidity conditions. This difference between them remains around 70 min as the inlet airflow absolute humidity increases.

The impact of the inlet airflow absolute humidity on the heat absorption by waterflow and the η_{th} of both TCES systems is depicted in Fig. 12. In both systems, the heat absorbed by waterflow increases slightly as the inlet airflow absolute humidity rises, with an increment of

Fig. 12. The influence of absolute humidity of reactor inlet airflow on the heat absorption by waterflow and discharging thermal efficiency of DFHEX-TCES and IBHEX-TCES systems.

less than 100 kJ observed when the absolute humidity increases from 7 g kg⁻¹ to 12 g kg⁻¹. However, the heat absorption by waterflow within the t_d nearly doubles within the same range of absolute humidity variation. At an absolute humidity of 12 g kg⁻¹, the heat absorption by waterflow within the t_d accounts for about 80 % of the total heat absorption over the complete process. The waterflow heat absorption of the DFHEX-TCES system consistently maintains a lead of more than 12 % compared to the IBHEX-TCES system in both the full process and within the t_d . Additionally, the overall system efficiency of both systems slightly increases with the rise in inlet air absolute humidity, with the η_{th} of the DFHEX-TCES system consistently exceeding that of the IBHEX-TCES system by about 10 percentage points.

Although the peak outlet waterflow temperature of the DFHEX-TCES system is lower compared to the IBHEX-TCES system, the difference is marginal. Nevertheless, in terms of the heat absorption by waterflow during the t_d and overall system efficiency, the DFHEX-TCES system consistently outperforms the IBHEX-TCES system. Overall, within a reasonable range of absolute humidity for the reactor inlet airflow, using the DFHEX instead of the IBHEX as the air-to-water HEX in TCES water heating systems proves feasible.

5.5. Effect of HRU heat transfer effectiveness

The HRU is a crucial component for both the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems. This section discusses the impact of the HRU heat transfer effectiveness on the discharging performance of these two TCES systems. Based on the commonly observed range of heat transfer effectiveness for HRUs, the heat transfer effectiveness of the HRU in this study is assumed to vary from 65 % to 85 %, while all other parameters remain consistent with those described in Section 5.1. The HRU heat transfer effectiveness does not significantly affect the peak outlet waterflow temperature of the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems, as shown in Fig. 13(a). As the HRU heat transfer effectiveness increases from 65 % to 85 %, there is only a slight increase in the peak outlet waterflow temperatures of both systems. While the rise in the HRU heat transfer effectiveness leads to more heat being recovered and thus increases the reactor inlet temperature, this does not translate into a proportional increase in outlet temperatures. This is because higher inlet temperatures slow down the hydration rate of the TCES composite materials within the reactor, leading to longer reaction times rather than a corresponding increase in outlet temperatures, as presented in Fig. 13 (b). When the HRU heat transfer effectiveness increases from 65 % to 85 %, the peak outlet waterflow temperatures of the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems experience a slight increase, rising from 34.86 °C to 34.19 °C–35.44 °C and 34.62 °C, respectively. However, the

Fig. 13. The impact of the HRU heat transfer effectiveness on (a) peak temperature of outlet waterflow, (b) time of complete discharging process; and (c) the heat absorption by waterflow and the discharging thermal efficiency of the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems.

completion time for the discharging process in the IBHEX-TCES and DFHEX-TCES systems extends by 212 min (a 28 % increase) and 191 min (a 23 % increase), respectively. These are reflected in the t_d , which also shows a similar proportionate increase. Moreover, the DFHEX-TCES system maintains a lead of about 1 h in the time taken to complete the discharging process compared to the IBHEX-TCES system. Across the entire simulation range, the IBHEX-TCES system consistently exhibits a peak outlet water flow temperature approximately 0.7 °C higher than the DFHEX-TCES system.

As the HRU heat transfer effectiveness improves from 65 % to 85 %, there is a significant increase in the η_{th} of both TCES systems as illustrated in Fig. 13(c). This increase is due to more heat being recycled back into the system. For instance, in the DFHEX-TCES system, the discharging thermal efficiency increases from 83 % ($Q_{ab} = 1297$ kJ) to 95 % ($Q_{ab} = 1480$ kJ), while in the IBHEX-TCES system, it rises from 72 % ($Q_{ab} = 1115$ kJ) to 85 % ($Q_{ab} = 1331$ kJ). Throughout the discharging process, the heat absorption by waterflow in the DFHEX-TCES system consistently exceeds that in the IBHEX-TCES system by over 10 %.

5.6. Effect of reaction bed configuration and HEX frontal area

Packed bed TCES reactors offer simplicity and ease of maintenance but face significant operational limitations in large-scale applications due to the low permeability and inadequate thermal conductivity of TCMs. These challenges become even more severe in thicker bed layers where uneven reactions lead to salt over-hydration, further diminishing their thermal performance [40,41]. To address these challenges, a multilayer TCES reactor comprising parallel packed bed units can be a preferred choice for large-scale systems. This configuration enhances the contact between TCMs and airflow, improving heat and mass transfer, reducing internal pressure drops, and thereby enhancing performance. In addition, it ensures a more uniform airflow distribution across the reaction beds, mitigating issues of salt over-hydration. In this study, two configurations are proposed to integrate the HEX into a multilayer TCES reactor for TCES water heating systems, including embedding a HEX

Fig. 14. Schematic diagram of the multilayer TCES reactor with DFHEX.

within the reaction beds to form the multilayer IBHEX-TCES system and installing a DFHEX that matches the IBHEX in size, at the reactor's end position to form the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system. The illustration of the multilayer DFHEX-TCES is presented in Fig. 14. Assuming equal mass flow rates of air per unit frontal area of the reaction bed at 0.00672 $\text{kg s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$ in both systems, the waterflow mass flow rate of each IBHEX unit in the multilayer IBHEX-TCES system is 0.0016 kg s^{-1} , with identical total water mass flow rates maintained across both configurations. The structural parameters for each reaction bed and HEX align with those outlined previously. This part investigates the impact of altering the ratio between the reaction bed and HEX frontal area (i.e., β) on both multilayer systems.

In the multilayer IBHEX-TCES system, where the reaction bed and IBHEX are integrated as a combined unit, the β value (i.e., the frontal area ratio of the reaction bed to that of HEX) is fixed at 1. As the number of reaction bed units (resulting in a larger frontal area of the reaction bed) increases, the system maintains a constant peak outlet waterflow temperature of 35.18 °C and thermal efficiency of 82 %. This constancy arises from the unchanged mass flow rate of air per unit frontal area of the reaction units. However, the inlet airflow mass flow rate increases proportionally with the number of reaction bed units. Consequently, this proportional increase results in a corresponding rise in the system's peak power and the amount of heat absorbed by the waterflow. Conversely, the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system performs differently, in which only one DFHEX matching the frontal area of the single IBHEX unit is placed at the end of the reactor. Consequently, the β value in the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system increases proportionally with the number of reaction bed units. The impact of the β on the discharging performance of the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system is shown in Fig. 15. The peak outlet waterflow temperature and η_{th} of the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system show a similar trend with increasing the β values. When the β increases from 1 to 5, the peak outlet waterflow temperature reaches its maximum at 35.24 °C and then begins to decrease as the β continues to rise. Similarly, the η_{th} of the system peaks at 95 % with $\beta = 5$. Fig. 15(c) illustrates that the DFHEX heat transfer effectiveness initially increases and then decreases with the increase in the mass flow rates of airflow and waterflow. It reaches a maximum of 95 % when the mass flow rate is five times that in Section 5.1, and then decreases with further increases in mass flow rate. This occurs because when the mass flow rate is below five times the benchmark (i.e., $\dot{m}_a = 0.0019$ kg s^{-1} and $\dot{m}_w = 0.0016$ kg s^{-1}), the overall heat transfer coefficient grows faster than the mass flow rate, resulting in an increased number of transfer units (NTU) for the DFHEX. However, when the mass flow rate surpasses five times the benchmark, the increase in the heat transfer coefficient lags the rise in mass flow, resulting in a decline in NTU.

Throughout the entire simulation range, although the peak outlet waterflow temperature of the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system is

Fig. 15. Influence of the frontal area ratio of the reactor bed to DFHEX on (a) peak temperature of outlet waterflow and peak heating power, (b) heat absorption by water, and discharging thermal efficiency in a multilayer DFHEX-TCES system; (c) effect of airflow and waterflow mass flow rate on the DFHEX heat transfer effectiveness.

generally lower than that of the multilayer IBHEX-TCES system, the difference never exceeds 0.6 °C. However, in terms of discharging thermal efficiency, the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system exhibits a significant advantage over the multilayer IBHEX-TCES system, with a maximum lead of nearly 15 percentage points. Additionally, in the multilayer DFHEX-TCES system, the peak power and heat absorption by waterflow increase proportionally with β , providing nearly the same power as the multilayer IBHEX-TCES system with the same number of reaction bed units. The results prove the feasibility of replacing the IBHEX with the DFHEX positioned at the end of the reactor in the

Table 5

Key performance results of four configurations of TCES water heating systems (reaction bed frontal velocity = 0.02 m • s⁻¹, reaction bed thickness = 0.05 m).

	TCM mass (g)	\dot{m}_a (kg/s)	\dot{m}_w (kg/s)	Peak T (°C)	Peak P (W)	$Q_{ab,w}$ (kJ)	η_{th} (%)
Single-layer IBHEX-TCES system	819	0.0019	0.0016	35.18	55	1272	82
Single-layer DFHEX-TCES system	882	0.0019	0.0016	34.59	51	1430	92
Multilayer IBHEX-TCES system	3276	0.0076	0.0064	35.18	219	5088	82
Multilayer DFHEX-TCES system	3528	0.0076	0.0064	35.17	217	5854	95

multilayer TCES systems.

Table 5 compares the key performance data of four configurations of TCES water heating systems when the frontal velocity of the reaction bed is 0.02 m s⁻¹. The data indicate that although the peak water temperature lift and peak power of the DFHEX-TCES system are slightly lower than those of the IBHEX-TCES system, its efficiency and the total heat absorbed by the water exceed those of the IBHEX-TCES system by more than 10 %, in both single-layer and multilayer systems. Moreover, as the scale of the reactor increases, both systems maintain the efficiency and peak water temperature lift levels of the single-layer system, showing no decrease with scaling up. At the same time, the output power and total heat absorbed by the water increase proportionally with the scale of the reactor, demonstrating the feasibility of multi-layer structures in TCES water heating systems.

6. Conclusion

This study numerically investigates the feasibility of a thermochemical energy storage (TCES) water heating system incorporating a detached finned microchannel flat tube heat exchanger (DFHEX) and a heat recovery unit (HRU), compared to a TCES system with an internal embedded bare microchannel heat exchanger (IBHEX) and an HRU. The feasibility of a multilayer DFHEX-TCES system for large-scale applications is also evaluated. The key findings are summarized as follows.

- (1) Both the finless structure IBHEX-TCES and DBHEX-TCES systems achieve a discharging thermal efficiency of around 80 %. The

- IBHEX-TCES system achieves a maximum temperature lift of 8.18 °C, which is 2 °C higher than that achieved by the DBHEX-TCES system. However, the finned DFHEX-TCES system significantly narrows this temperature gap and surpasses both finless systems by more than 10 percentage points in discharging thermal efficiency.
- (2) With variations in the inlet temperatures of airflow and waterflow, both systems exhibit similar trends in maximum waterflow temperature lift and discharging thermal efficiency: both increase with rising inlet airflow temperature and decrease with rising inlet waterflow temperature. While the maximum waterflow temperature rise is slightly higher in the IBHEX-TCES system, the DFHEX-TCES system significantly outperforms discharging thermal efficiency, leading by up to 10 percentage points.
 - (3) With increased airflow mass flow rate, peak outlet waterflow temperatures rise for both systems, while increased water flow mass flow rate lowers them. Conversely, the discharging thermal efficiency of the two systems exhibits a trend opposite to that of the peak outlet waterflow temperatures when changes in airflow and water flow mass flow rates occur. The DFHEX system consistently achieves up to 12 percentage points higher discharging thermal efficiency than the IBHEX system.
 - (4) As the absolute humidity of the airflow increases, the peak outlet waterflow temperatures of both systems rise with the gap between them widening. At an absolute humidity of 12 g kg⁻¹, the temperate difference between the two systems reaches 1.29 °C. The system's thermal efficiency also increases by nearly 5 percentage points from 7 g kg⁻¹ to 12 g kg⁻¹ absolute humidity. Additionally, the heat absorption by waterflow with a temperature lift >5 °C increases substantially, with a rise of over 70 % in the proportion of total energy absorbed by waterflow, exceeding 30 percentage points. Across the entire process, the DFHEX-TCES system outputs over 12 % more heat via waterflow compared to the IBHEX-TCES system.
 - (5) When the HRU effectiveness increases from 65 % to 85 %, both systems experience a notable extension in the discharging process duration, with an additional 212 min (a 28 % increase) for the IBHEX-TCES system and 191 min (a 23 % increase) for the DFHEX-TCES system. The discharging thermal efficiency improves from 72 % to 85 % for the IBHEX-TCES system and from 83 % to 95 % for the DFHEX-TCES system.

- (6) In multilayer TCES systems, the DFHEX configuration demonstrates a peak outlet waterflow temperature that initially rises and then declines with changes in the ratio (β) of the reaction bed to the DFHEX frontal area. The peak temperature reaches 35.4 °C when $\beta = 5$, surpassing the IBHEX configuration. At other ratios, the temperature remains within 0.6 °C lower than the IBHEX system. Nevertheless, the DFHEX configuration consistently outperforms the IBHEX system by approximately 10 percentage points in discharging thermal efficiency.

In conclusion, within a reasonable range of operational parameters, the detached finned heat exchanger (DFHEX) proves to be an effective replacement for internal microchannel flat tube heat exchangers (IBHEX) in open TCES water heating systems as well as in large-scale multilayer TCES systems. The DFHEX offers notable advantages, including simplified system design and reduced maintenance requirements. Future research will focus on developing and testing a comprehensive multilayer DFHEX-TCES system to evaluate its practical performance across various real-world conditions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Yong Zhang: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ziwei Chen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jianbin Chen:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Yuehong Su:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology. **Saffa Riffat:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Nomenclature

A_{freq}	Pre-exponential Arrhenius factor, s ⁻¹	Greek symbols	
C	Specific heat, J•g ⁻¹ •K ⁻¹	ρ	Density, kg•m ⁻³
c	Mole concentration, mol•m ⁻³	ε	porosity
D_g	Gas diffusivity in reactor bed, m ² •s ⁻¹	α	Reaction conversion degree
d	Thickness or depth, m	η	Efficiency, %
E_a	Arrhenius activation energy, J•mol ⁻¹	μ	Dynamic viscosity, Pa•s
ΔH_r	Enthalpy of reaction, J•mol ⁻¹	λ	Thermal conductivity, W•m ⁻¹ •K ⁻¹
HEX	Heat exchanger	β	Ratio of frontal areas
HRU	Heat recovery unit	Subscripts	
h	Heat transfer coefficient, W•m ⁻² •K ⁻¹	a	Air
k	Permeability, m ²	ab	Heat absorbed
M	Molecular mass, g•mol ⁻¹	amb	Ambient
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate, kg•s ⁻¹	Al	Aluminium
\mathbf{n}	Normal vector toward exterior	dis	Discharging
P	Pressure, Pa	eff	Effective
\mathbf{q}	Conductive heat flux, W•m ⁻²	eq	Equilibrium state
Q	Heat, J	f	Final
R	Universal gas constant, J•mol ⁻¹ •K ⁻¹	i	Initial
R_{kin}	Kinetic factor, s ⁻¹	in	Inlet
ΔS_r	Entropy, J•mol ⁻¹ •K ⁻¹	int	interval
S_w	Mass source of water vapor, kg•m ⁻³ •s ⁻¹	ins	Insulation plate

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T	Temperature, K or °C	kin	Kinetic
TCES	Thermochemical energy storage	w	Water
t	Time, s or min	re	Heat release
\vec{u}	Velocity vector, $\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	out	Outlet
V	Volume of salt bed, m^3		
z	Stoichiometric number		

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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